

pH 7.8 with 176 kg available N, 5.13 kg P, and 164.3 kg K/ha. A bed 5 × 1 m was prepared to raise the nursery (Jaya variety). Treatments are given in the table. Farmyard manure (FYM) was applied at 15 t/ha to all treatments, to ease uprooting of seedlings. Treatments were sampled 25 d after sowing to analyze growth and N and P content.

Seedlings were transplanted in the main field with 90 kg N, 13.04 kg P, and 24.89 kg K/ha. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Seedlings responded significantly to N and P (Table 1). Height and weight of

Table 2. Effect of fertilized seedlings on grain and straw yield.

Nursery treatment	Yield (t/ha)					
	Grain			Straw		
	Year 1	Year 2	Av	Year 1	Year 2	Av
No N	2.5	2.5	2.5	4.4	4.3	4.4
100 kg N/ha	2.8	2.7	2.8	5.0	4.8	4.9
200 kg N/ha	3.1	3.1	3.1	5.5	5.4	5.4
No P	2.7	2.7	2.7	7.8	4.7	4.7
21.5 kg P/ha	2.8	2.8	2.8	5.0	4.8	4.9
43.0 kg P/ha	2.9	2.8	2.9	5.1	5.0	5.1
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.2		0.3	0.3	

seedlings increased, and N and P contents increased.

Yield of grain and straw was significantly higher with N-fertilized seedlings

(Table 2). No response to P was found, possibly because of the FYM added to the nursery. ■

Crop management

Effects of number of axillary buds and main crop cutting time on ratoon crop yield

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We studied the effects on ratoon crop yield of the number of axillary buds sprouting and of different cutting times for the main crop of hybrid rice variety Shanyou 63. Planting density of the main crop was 28 hills/m² with 120-60-60 kg NPK/ha as basal fertilizer and 69 kg N/ha as topdressing 15 d after full heading, to promote bud sprouting. The crop was cut at 33 cm height at different times after main crop heading. The experimental results are shown in the table.

Number of axillary buds were significantly correlated with carbohydrate content and weight of stem and sheath, which increased as cutting time of the main crop was delayed. The correlation coefficients were $r = 0.9676$ and $r = 0.9950$.

These results show that starch content of the axillary buds was increased by the photosynthate of leaves before the main crop matured.

Cutting time of the main crop was significantly correlated with yield of the main crop and number of axillary buds sprouting, number of productive panicles, and yield of the ratoon crop. Regression equations were

Number of axillary buds and productive panicles, and yield of ratoon rice with different cutting times of the main crop. Southern Sichuan, China, 1989.

Item	Cutting time (d after main crop heading)				
	22 d	25 d	28 d	31 d	34 d
Dry weight of stem and sheath of main crop (g/hill)	12.51	12.31	12.88	13.87	16.91
Carbohydrate content of stem and sheath of main crop (%)	1.6	2.2	1.8	2.1	8.6
Maturity of main crop grain at cutting (%)	61.5	64.7	77.6	84.7	100.0
Number of axillary buds sprouting before main crop harvest (no./m ²)	0.00	0.00	0.84	3.64	27.16
Maximum number of axillary buds sprouting (no./m ²)	221.2	126.0	128.8	207.2	274.4
Productive panicles in ratoon crop (no/m ²)	187.6	123.3	126.0	187.6	257.6
Grain yield of ratoon crop (t/ha)	1.5	1.4	1.1	1.3	1.8
Grain yield of main crop (t/ha)	6.4	7.3	7.7	7.7	8.1

Grain yield of the main crop	$\hat{y} = 257.8133 + 8.4867x$
Number of axillary buds sprouting	$\hat{y} = 87.4946 - 6.1322x + 0.1135x^2$
Ratoon crop panicle number	$\hat{y} = 68.8988 - 4.83x + 0.0906x^2$
Grain yield of ratoon crop	$\hat{y} = 772.9456 - 50.8443x + 0.9274x^2$

Cutting the main crop 34 d after heading, when axillary buds began sprouting, resulted in the highest yields for both the main crop and the ratooning crop. Yield of the ratoon crop was attributed to higher numbers of productive panicles. ■

Integrated pest management – diseases

Diseases of rice in Cameroon

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Rice is a relatively new crop in Cameroon; it is currently grown on about 20,000 ha of irrigated and upland fields. Irrigated rice accounts for more than 90% of the land area under rice and contributes about 94% of annual production (Table 1). Upland rice is grown as a subsistence crop by peasant farmers in isolated areas of the country.

The Cameroonian farmer is constrained by a number of abiotic, biotic, and socioeconomic factors. Among the biotic factors, diseases pose the most problems, causing yield losses of 10-30% every year.

Development of varieties with resistance to major diseases would help stabilize rice production. We carried out disease surveys in 1988 wet season (Jul-Dec) and 1989 dry season (Jan-May) to more precisely define the rice disease situation for input to the rice improvement program.